

READINESS ON ONLINE DISTANCE LEARNING: ITS IMPACT TO THE MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT OF FIRST-YEAR STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine which domain of Readiness on Online Distance Learning can best predict Mathematics Achievement in Mathematics in the Modern World (MMW). A Predictive- correlational method of research was conducted using an adapted and researcher-made questionnaire validated by the experts. The extent of Readiness on Online Distance Learning has the following indicators: technology access, technology skills, study skills, time management skills and motivation adapted from the study of Tuntirojanawong (2013) using the 25-item questions. On the other hand, the researcher's test questionnaire was utilized to determine the mathematics achievements of the first-year students in Mathematics in the Modern World Subject. The statistical tools used were mean, standard deviation, Pearson's product-moment correlation, and multiple regression. It was revealed that the Readiness on Online Distance Learning was evident among first-year students. In addition, the level of mathematics is moderately satisfactory with an average of 2.50 equivalent to the range (80-82%). The null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance to test the correlation of variables. Results show that there is a significant very weak positive correlation between the readiness on online distance learning and Mathematics Achievements. Furthermore, Technology Skills is the indicator of Readiness on Online Distance Learning that best predicts the Mathematics Achievement of first-year students.

Keywords: *Readiness on Online Distance Learning, Mathematics Achievement, Predictive-Correlational Design, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is one of the subjects wherein students are encouraged to master because it is important in the scientific and technological development of countries. However, it was found out that students' mathematics achievement in our country continued to decline, and the participation of the Philippines in Trend in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) confirmed this bad and shocking condition based on the report posted last 2013. The report added that the achievements of Filipino students in National and International surveys on mathematics lag its neighboring countries like Singapore, South Korea, Hong Kong, Chinese Taipei, and Japan. Thus, even college students from different colleges and universities in the country are not exempted from the problems of low mathematical achievements (Care et.al., 2014).

The global pandemic of COVID-19 has fundamentally affected nearly every area of life, including education. Concerning the issue, student online learning readiness (OLR) is identified as being an important predictor of online learning such as computer skills for social interaction, social communication, and learning outcomes (Kubiatko & Vlckoya, 2010). This is similar to the study of Watkins and Triner (2003) stated that online distance readiness is important for enhancing the delivery, interaction, and facilitation of teaching and learning processes. In addition, the Philippines Commission on Higher Education encouraged higher education institutions (HEIs) to continue with alternative modes of education. As an emergency response to the pandemic, online distance became the modal solution for various academic institutions (Joaquin et al., 2020). Thus, the implementation of any online distance education should be preceded by the measurement of readiness so that the institution can design a suitable and appropriate system to fit learning requirements (Chen & Fu, 2009).

In Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology (ASSCAT), Trento Campus, common problems had been observed by the researchers and that was the sudden shift in the education system that leads to a decline in the student's mathematics achievement. The increase in the number of dropouts and students who got an In-process (IP) grade in GE 4 (Mathematics in the Modern World) subject became a problematic issue on the campus since the beginning of the new normal setting. It is the innermost reason that the researcher is interested in conducting a study to determine if there is a significant influence of readiness for online distance learning on the mathematics achievements of first-year students.

The researcher is eager to fill the gap in the literature and seek to establish information on the influence of readiness on online distance learning on the mathematics achievements of first-year students to become a basis for the making of interventions for school administrators and instructors and to be more productive in developing the mathematics achievement of students. Understanding also if readiness for online distance learning among students can relate to the mathematics achievements of the students is a good step in addressing the needs of students to improve their mathematics performance in the time of difficulties of this new normal education.

Research Questions

The main goal of this research was to determine which domain of Readiness on Online Distance Learning can best predict the Mathematics Achievement of first-year students in Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology- Trento Satellite Campus.

Specifically, it attended to the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of Student's Readiness on Online Distance Learning when measured according to:
 - 1.1 Technology Access
 - 1.2 Technology Skills
 - 1.3 Study Skills
 - 1.4 Time Management Skills
 - 1.5 Motivation
2. To assess the level of Mathematics Achievements among the first-year students of ASSCAT, Trento Campus.
3. To determine the significant relationship between Readiness on Online Distance Learning and Mathematics Achievement among the first-year students of ASSCAT, Trento Satellite Campus.
4. To determine which of the domains of Readiness on Online Distance Learning can best predict the Mathematics Achievement of students in Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology- Trento Satellite Campus.

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research design, specifically the Predictive-correlational technique to investigate which domains of Readiness on Online Distance Learning can best predict the Mathematics Achievements of First Year students. Further, the respondents of the study were first-year students of Agusan Del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology (ASSCAT), Trento Satellite Campus who enrolled during the first semester, S.Y. 2021-2022. There were 284 total samples from the first-year students of BEED, BSEd-English, BSEd-Math, Applied Math, and AB-English which were obtained using Universal sampling. In addition, data gathering was done through online survey questionnaires through Google Forms after the researchers collected informed consent from the respondents. The procedure is deemed appropriate in the context of the pandemic and following the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) for management of emerging infectious disease resolution no. 38 series of 2020.

Moreover, the research instruments of this study consist of two parts. The first part is the independent variable which is Readiness on Online Distance Learning was adapted from the study of Tuntirojanawong (2013). It used a four-point Likert scale (4- Strongly Agree, 3- Agree, 2- Disagree, and 1- Strongly disagree). The second part is the dependent variable which is Mathematics Achievements which was determined using the

researcher's exam in the final term topics under GE 4 (Mathematics in the Modern World) subject. The researcher's exam underwent a pilot testing and item analysis of the selected students. Thus, the expert validators of the test questionnaire played a big part in the success of determining the appropriate validity and reliability of the questionnaires. Using Kuder Richardson Formula (KR20), the test of internal consistency gives a value of 0.75 which means high and acceptable. The study utilized Mean, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation, and regression analysis to measure students' readiness for online distance learning and their mathematics achievements, identifying which domains significantly predict these outcomes.

RESULTS

Table 1. Level of Readiness on Online Distance Learning

Readiness on Online Distance Learning	Mean	Description
Technology Access	2.58	High
Technology Skills	2.94	High
Study Skills	2.73	High
Time Management Skills	2.84	High
Motivation	2.93	High
Overall Mean	2.80	High

Table 2. Level of Mathematics Achievement in GE 4 (Mathematics in the Modern World)

Grade Scale	Equivalence	Descriptive Rating	Frequency	Percentage
1.00	98-100	Excellent	0	0%
1.25	95-97	Outstanding	0	0%
1.50	92-94	Very Good	4	1%
1.75	89-91	Very Satisfactory	10	4%
2.00	86-88	Good Work	32	11%
2.25	83-85	Satisfactory	41	14%
2.50	80-82	Moderately Satisfactory	60	22%
2.75	77-79	Quit Good Work	28	10%
3.00	75-76	Passing	51	18%
5.00	Below 75	Fail	58	20%
TOTAL			284	100%
Total Average		2.50	Moderately Satisfactory	

Table 3. Significance of the Relationship between Readiness on Online Distance Learning and Mathematics Achievement

Readiness on Online Distance Learning	Mathematics Achievement		
	r-value	p-value	Remarks
Technology Access	0.001	0.993	Not Significant
Technology Skills	0.189	0.001	Significant
Study Skills	0.118	0.047	Significant
Time Management Skills	0.127	0.032	Significant
Motivation	0.134	0.024	Significant
Overall	0.13	0.03	Significant

Table 4. Multiple Regression Analysis in determining which domain of Readiness on Online Distance Learning can best predict the Mathematics Achievement

Readiness on Online Distance Learning	Standardize Coefficient	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Technology Access	0.089	1.514	0.132	Not Significant
Technology Skills	0.624	9.607	0.031	Significant
Study Skills	0.111	1.766	0.079	Not Significant
Time Management Skills	0.065	1.102	0.271	Not Significant
Motivation	0.242	3.846	0.048	Significant

DISCUSSION

The level of readiness for online distance learning in terms of the specified indicators obtained an overall mean score of 2.80 which is high. This implies that the readiness for online distance learning among first-year students in ASSCAT, Trento Satellite Campus is evident. The result is similar to the study of Hashim and Osman (2021) revealed that readiness to use e-learning among science students in Tunku Abdul Rahman Putra Form Six College (KiSTARP) is also high. Among the indicators of Student readiness in online learning, Technology Skills got the highest mean of 2.94 which means high. This implies that Technology Skills is evident among the first-year students of ASSCAT, Trento Satellite Campus. Rodrigues et.al (2019) supported the idea that the basic technical skills of devices, together with the Internet, provide students and teachers greater access to online resources for teaching-learning. These skills influence students' academic performance (Lopez & Jose, 2013).

On the other hand, the level of the mathematics achievements of first-year students in the subject of GE 4 (Mathematics in the Modern World) is moderately satisfactory with an average score of 2.50 which is equivalent to the range of 80-82%. The result implied that Students' Mathematics Achievement is moderately Satisfying under the implementation of the new normal Setting in ASSCAT, Trento Satellite Campus. Similar to the findings of Garinganao & Bearneza (2021) where respondents show approaching satisfactory mathematic achievements. Moreover, Peteros et.al., (2020) showed an almost similar result of the approaching moderate performance on the respondents in the study conducted at a Public National High School, in Cebu, Philippines. Additionally, it was also found that the majority of the respondents, 60 students from 284 have a score of 2.50 which is equivalent to 80-82. In addition, 51 students from 284 got a 3.0 which is equivalent to 75-76% indicating that 18% of the respondents with a descriptive rating of passing score. However, 58 students out of 284 got a score of 75 below that is about 8% of the total students. This implies that 8% of the total respondents fail to pass the given final examination.

With regards to the relationship between Readiness for Online Distance Learning and Mathematics Achievement shows a significant very weak positive correlation reflected in Pearson's r which is 0.130, with a p -value of 0.03 showing $p < .05$ level of significance set in this study. This implies that if Readiness on Online Distance Learning among students increases or decreases, their Mathematics Achievement also increases or decrease, although the relationship is very weak. The study of Bovermann, Weidlich, and Bastiaens (2018) in Hagen Germany supports that there was a significant positive correlation found between students' online learning readiness in the dimension of technical competencies. This is like the study of Navani and Ansari (2016) stated that online distance readiness is important for enhancing the delivery, interaction, and facilitation of teaching and learning processes. Moreover, Wang & Guo (2022) highlighted online learning readiness showed a significant positive relationship with online academic performance during COVID-19. These results demonstrated that being ready to study online and having high emotional competence could make adolescents more resilient toward COVID-19 related challenges and help them learn more effectively online.

The Multiple Regression analysis gleaned that among the indicators of Readiness on Online distance learning, Technology Skills, and Motivation significantly predict the Mathematics Achievement of first-year students because of its p -value of 0.031 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance set in this study. Moreover, among the two indicators, Technology Skills is considered as the best predictor because it has the highest standardized coefficient of 0.624. This result supports the claim of Saenz (2015) that the basic technical skills of devices, together with the Internet, provide students and teachers greater access to online resources for teaching-learning. These skills influence students' academic performance (Lopez & Jose, 2013).

Conclusions

Based on the results, it is indicated that the student's readiness on online distance learning is high and evident. Moreover, students' Mathematics Achievements is

moderately satisfactory in the Ge 4 (Mathematics in the Modern World) subject. It was perceived that the high readiness on online distance learning has a significant relationship to the improvement of Mathematics achievement, however weak relationship was observed. In addition, Technology Skill was found to be the best predictor of Readiness on Online Distance Learning helping to improve the Mathematics achievements of the student. Moreover, the teachers must exert extra drive and passion on their teaching specifically in modular learning and Asynchronous platform since it was found out that most of the students have difficulty in the internet connection at home.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. ASSCAT, Trento Satellite campus should find any means to develop the readiness on online distance learning of the next incoming first-year students since it was found that high readiness on online distance learning and has a significant relation to good mathematics achievements.
2. Students should be more innovative and trained with new technology that can be useful in their studies to improve their academic performance. They should exert effort in their study because access to the internet at home is not essential to performing at school.
3. Instructors/Teacher shall provide technical assistance to the students to access the learning materials. Also, initial orientation to the students in the platform utilized in the class should be given promptly.
4. School Administrators should plan a learning strategy or method that is appropriate to use in online learning and to plan an alternative way to continue the teaching-learning process despite of pandemic to enhance student learning skills. Hence, readiness on online distance learning has a significant relationship to mathematics achievements, then this variable should be considered by the administrator even after the pandemic crises.
5. Future Researchers should explore other factors that can be related to mathematics achievements since it was found that readiness on online distance learning has very weak relationship to the Mathematics Achievement of the students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to ethical guidelines set by the ACN Research Committee and followed the steps below in the gathering of data.

Seeking Permission to Conduct the Study. The researchers made a letter to ask permission to the college president of Agusan Del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology (ASSCAT). After the approval, the researcher wrote another letter

request to inform the Campus Administrator of ASSCAT, Trento Satellite campus about the conduct of the study.

Conduct of the Study. Informed consent forms were secured, providing participants with information about the study's purpose, rights, risks, benefits, safety, privacy, confidentiality protocols, and the researcher's qualifications. Data was collected online using Google Forms, following health protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force on Infectious Diseases (IATF). Then, the researchers administered the survey questionnaire and examination for the final term to the first-year students of Agusan Del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology (ASSCAT), Trento Satellite Campus through the Google form platform. The researcher ensured that respondents were well-oriented as to the mere purpose of the instrument and assured that the data gathered will be treated with the utmost confidentiality.

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REFERENCES

- Bovermann, K., Weidlich, J., & Bastiaens, T. (2018). Online learning readiness and attitudes towards gaming in gamified online learning—a mixed methods case study. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 15(1), 1-17.
- Care, E., Azim, F., Beswick, B., Harding, S. M., Luo, R., Bustos, T., & Cagasan, L. (2015). Large-scale assessments for use in the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/deref/http%3A%2F%2Fbit.ly%2F2G0PvYq>
- Chen, S. Y., & Fu, Y. C. (2009). Internet use and academic achievement: gender differences in early adolescence. *Adolescence*, 44(176), 797–842.
- Warner, R.M. (2013). *Applied statistics: From bivariate through multivariate techniques*. Thousand Oaks, CA. Sage Publications.
- Hashim, N., & Osman, K. (2020). Students' knowledge of the readiness to use E-Learning. *International Journal of Academic Research. Conf. Ser.* 1700 012033.
- Garinganao, N & Bearneza, F. (2018). Algebraic skills and academic achievements in mathematics of grade 7 students in Philippines Chinese school. *Philippine Social Science Journal*. DOI:<https://doi.org/main.v4i3.396>

- Hashim, N. H. C., & Osman, K. (2021). Students' Knowledge of the Readiness to Use E-Learning. *Learning*, 10(2), 596-604.
- Joaquin, J. J. B., Biana, H. T., & Dacela, M. A. (2020, October). The Philippine higher education sector in the time of COVID-19. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 5, p. 576371). Frontiers.
- Kubiatko, M., & Vlckova, K. (2010). The relationship between ICT use and science knowledge for Czech students: a secondary analysis of PISA. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 8(3), 523–543.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10763-010-9195-6>
- Lopez-Islas & Jose, R. (2013). Digital literacy and academic success in online education for underprivileged communities: The prep@net case. Doctoral dissertation, The University of Texas at Austin. <http://hdl.handle.net/2152/20948>
- Navani, Y., & Ansari, M. A. (2016). A study of e-learning readiness of university faculty. *International Journal of Current Research*, 8(8), 35752-35756.
- Peteros, E., Gamboa, A., Etcuban, J., Dinauan, A., Sito, R., & Arcadio, R. (2020). Factors affecting mathematics performance of junior high school students. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*. e-ISSN: 1306-3030. 2020, Vol 15, em0556. <http://doi.org/10.29333/iejm/5938>
- Rodrigues, A.L.; Cerdeira, L.; Machado-Taylor, M.d.L.; Alves, H. (2021). Technological Skills in Higher Education—Different Needs and Different Uses. *Educ. Sci.* 2021, 11, 326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11070326>
- Saenz, R.M. (2015). The relationship between technology skills performance and academic achievements among 8th grade students: A canonical Analysis. Texas A&M University Corpus Christi. Retrieved from <https://tamuccir.tdl.org/handle/1969.6/623>
- Tuntirojanawong, S. (2013). Students' readiness for E-learning : A case study *Journal Of Learning In Higher Education*, 9(1), 59–66.
- Wang, Y., Xia, M., Guo, W. Academic performance under COVID-19: The role of online learning readiness and emotional competence. *Curr Psychol* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-02699-7>
- Watkins, L., & Triner, D. (2003). Assessing readiness for e-learning. *Performance Improvement Quarterly*, 17(4) 66- 79
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